

<p>Particles in the Dictionarium Latino-Epiroticum of Frang Bardhi (1635)</p>		<p>Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: particles, suffixes, dictionary, verbal system, Meshari, Latin words, etc.</p>
<p>Dorentina Xhafa</p>	<p>University of Tirana, Albania.</p>	
<p>Abstract</p> <p>The Dictionarium latino-epiroticum represents a significant importance for the history of Albanian language and its evolution. It is not only one the oldest texts in Albanian, but, first of all, it is important, because with this dictionary begins the Albanian lexicography.</p>		

Contance of the dictionary³⁰

The dictionary contains around 4500 Latin words and 2500 corresponding ones in Albanian. The author has gained different appendixes called chapters:

1. Numbers
2. Masculine and feminine names
3. Toponyms of Albania
4. Adverbs
5. Prepositions
6. Exclamation
7. Proverbs

The verbal system of the dictionary is relatively fruitful. The most frequent verbal forms, preconceiving that it is a dictionary, are the particles, especially the gerund.

Verbal system of Albanian includes some forms of the particles; some of them are inherited, and some others are created in the inner development of the language.³¹

Our study is not only a simple view of the verbal forms, but even a comparative approach to our prior study of *Meshari*'s verbal system, the oldest book found in Albanian.

Thus, the study reveals those forms which represent an evolution phase compared to *Meshari* and considers the forms of a morphological significance. The analysis is not only an isolated

³⁰ For our study is used the critical edition of the *Dictionarium latino-epiroticum*, by Bardhyl Demiraj. Bardhi, F, *Dictionarium Latino-Epiroticum (Romae 1635) per R.D. Franciscum Blanchum*, (botim kritik nga Bardhyl Demiraj), Botime Françeskane, Shkodër, 2008.

³¹ Topalli, K., *Sistemifoljor i gjuhëshqipe*, Plejad, Tiranë, 2010, pp. 443-444.

research, but it has been done considering it as an important link in all the Albanian language evolution.

A. The participle

Albanian has only one participle, which pertains to the past and generally has a passive character, but in distinction from other languages, it is presented in numerous and various forms, some of which are inherited from the Indo-European, whereas some others have been formed in the inner development by the attach of the suffixes of this form. But the Albanian participle has lost the grammatical categories of gender and number being presented only in verbal characteristics; consequently, it cannot express grammatical categories that are typical of the nominal-adjectival system.³²

Participle in this dictionary appears with these suffixes: *-m*, *-unë*, *-ë*, *-n^dë*, *-jtun(ë)*, *-të*, *-tunë*.

- With the suffix **-m**

Bām, besuem, biruem, bumbëlluem, çirkuem, çmuem, çpeituum, dëftuum, dërguem, dëshëruem etc.

This diphthong, at Bardhi is *-ue-*, while at Buzuku is *-uo-*; e.g..

Buzuku: *afruom* (20 43), *besuom* (186 22), *çmuom* (306 62), *dëshëruom* (250 20), *forcuom* (288 22) etj.

Bardhi: *afruem, besuem, çmuem, dëshëruem, forcuem etc.*

- With the suffix **-unë**

avitunë, bdeshunë, begenisunë, brītunë, davitunë, derdhunë, dëlirunë, diegunë, druetunë, dhimtunë, grabitunë, grishunë etc.

- With the suffix **-ë**

Dalë, dierrë, falë, folë, këlbazë, marrë, mbëledhë, mbërshëlë, mbiellë, mielë, nçelë, nxierrë, përmierrë, përshitiellë, piellë, siellë, shkelë, shqerrë, thirrë, vielë, viellë, vierrë.

- With the suffix **-n^dë**

Dhanë, kienë, përzanë, ngranë, lanë, nξανë, zanë.

- With the suffix **-jtun(ë)**

Mbaitunë (bāitunë), muitunë, prueitunë, ruoitunë (ruitunë, rueitunë).

- With the suffix **-të**

Sëmutë (to Buzuku we find *sëmutë* 266 23, and even *sëmunë* 32 83); *thatë*; and *votë*.

- With the suffix **-tunë**

³²Topalli, K., *Sistemifoljor i gjuhëshqipe*, Plejad, Tiranë, 2010, p. 654.

Dritunë, dridhtunë.

B. Analytic forms based on the participle

Analytic forms based on the participle (historically infinitive) are: the gerund *tue punue/duke punue*, the privative form *pa punue/pa punuar* and the Gheg infinitive *me punue*. The first two forms pertain to both dialects, whereas the last form pertains only to Gheg. All these forms have no person, nor number, nor mood, but they only have the category of voice, the non-active form being distinguished by the particle *u*, that is placed before the body of the verb.³³

Analytic forms based on the participle found in Bardhi's dictionary in comparison to Buzuku, are: Buzuku: *me shpërblenë* (38 70), while Bardhi: *me çpërblēm*, thus, the same verb, with different suffixes.

Buzuku: *me gjellë* (350 46), while Bardhi: *me gjellunë*.

Buzuku: *me nëbëljedhunë* (362 19), while Bardhi represents two forms: *me mbëledhë* (with the suffix -ë) and *me mbëliedhunë* (with the suffix -unë).

Buzuku: two forms of: *me pitë* (60 31) and *me pinë* (152 64), while Bardhi has only the form: *me pīm*.

Conclusions

The dictionary contains different suffixes that form the Albanian participle. Compared to the actual language, there are evolutions, which are connected with the time when the book is written, but represent even dialectal features. Compared to Buzuku, Bardhi represents a more evaluated phase of the verbal system, connected to a morphologic character, but mostly to a phonetic one.

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³³Topalli, K., *Sistemifoljor i gjuhëshqipe*, Plejad, Tiranë, 2010, p. 660.

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